

The Communication Skills in Compliance with the Ethics of Caring for the Elderly People

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ABSTRACT: The communication skills in compliance with the ethics of caring for the elderly people are a form of communication interaction based on principles, rules and basic regulations labeled by specialists. They are characterized by a focus on the relationship with the elderly people or with a group of elderly people to achieve good results. The people who take care of them participate in the communication interaction, respect the communication style and aim to obtain a result by solving the assigned tasks and reaching the established objects. The ability to lead a conversation with the elderly people competently means a correct understanding of the particularities of the personal characteristics of the elderly, their goals, objectives and interests. These can be considered determining factors for improving and increasing the quality of their life.

KEYWORDS: communication, communication skills, elderly people, ethics

Introduction

As you get older, the vulnerability to disease increases, diseases are more easily contacted, the evolution is more pronounced and lasting, an illness can create social worker blockages in the relationship with vulnerable seniors can also be understood as a philosophy on morality. Due to the vulnerability of this social category, the need for social service is highlighted by an increasing number of elderly people, compared to all other disadvantaged people. Specialists are expected to work in full collaboration with the elderly people in need, pursuing their major interests, but also according attention to the rest of the people involved.

In this sense, the professional ethics of specialist specialized in working with the elderly people is a decisive factor in elucidating the moral problems of dependent elderly people through a cognitive approach, regulating both the professional relations of specialist with reference to standards of conduct in relations with beneficiaries, in our case in the relationship with the elderly persons in difficulty, as well as with colleagues or other categories of professionals.

Content

There are certain techniques by which you can direct the attention of the elderly in your direction. The “proper name” technique is based on the obligatory pronunciation of the elderly person's name aloud. The “mirror of attitude” means that a smile on the face will instead provoke a smile, and an ugly grimace, on the contrary. A pleasant facial expression attracts the elderly man's attention. Congratulations are welcome in any conversation. They contain a slight exaggeration of the merits of the elderly, such as: How beautifully you dressed today! / Today you are in a good mood! / How beautifully you arranged your room! However, it is necessary to distinguish compliments from exaggerated praise, which consists in an exaggeration of the merits of the elderly. “Communication with the elderly is a science, an art and a plus of humanity, intelligence and prediction with which God endows some of his fellows” said the famous Mother Teresa (CEPECOM 2010).

Therefore, in the development of research and care practice of the elderly people, the following aspects are taken into account as a priority:

- the population of the elderly is growing, both numerically and proportionally;

- there is a close connection between the third age and the risk situation presented by the bio-psycho-social disabilities specific to the elderly;

- the social and medical protection system, as it is currently organized, is not yet fully able to meet the specific needs of this age group (Țigmeanu and Keller 2008, 3).

DeMont and Piemont says: communication, respectively the transmission of information or messages, has certain specificities in the case of working with the elderly. These are due to the physiological, psychological and social peculiarities of individuals belonging to a special population category. the group of older people they work with should respond appropriately to the proposed program of activities.

The peculiarities that influence the communication with the elderly people are related to:

- hearing and vision functions, which decrease;
- decrease in speech speed and voice volume, mainly due to decreased performance of the respiratory system; this impediment, in many cases present even at rest;
- the ability to communicate, to give answers, or to take over the messages sent by the social workers, is related to the elderly and to the decrease of the reaction speed in general. This decrease in reaction speed also affects memory (especially short-term memory), and decreases speech speed;
- facial expression and expressiveness, which are reduced in spectrum and which has not only some explanations related to the mental state (more depressed, more depressed) characteristic of this age, but also to some anatomical-histological changes. Thus, according to relatively recent research, the grumpy/angry/angry face of the elderly is also due to the significant decrease in fat from the fibers that make up the muscles of the face;
- sleep problems and its peculiarities (DeMont and Peatman 1993, 21-23).

The European Union recognizes and respects above all the rights of older people who are more likely to become dependent on care, to lead a dignified and independent life and to participate in social and cultural life (EU Charter of Fundamental Rights, Article 25) . Any restriction of these rights, if caused by age and dependency, must remain in clear legal grounds, transparent legal procedures, must be proportionate, reviewable, and even consider the party concerned with the highest interest. Neglect and disregard for these rights should be considered unacceptable. Member States should develop policies that promote these rights, at home and in care institutions, and support individuals to enforce them.

The principles underlying the fundamental values of social assistance are the provision of services in support of the beneficiaries, respectively of the elderly person in difficulty, respect for the dignity and uniqueness of the individual, the confidentiality and integrity of the person, self-determination and professional competence. Each social worker has acquired these values and principles, which will be found in his behavior, so as not to harm through his actions the image of the social worker profession (Țigmeanu and Keller 2008, 4). The social worker specialized in working with the elderly people needs to respect their rights (European Charter 2010, 4-14):

- the right to dignity (the right to respect and the defense of dignity), physical welfare (the right to health and access to institutions in this field) and mental, freedom and security (economic security and material security);
- psychological and emotional well-being;
- protection against medical and pharmaceutical abuse;
- the right to self-determination (the right to express the desire and choose the activity, the right to choose the place of living);
- right to privacy (the right to choose one's place and way of life);
- the right to high quality and adapted care (the right to care and help, the right to care granted by qualified personnel (the right to medical care);
- the right to continuous communication, participation and cultural activity
- the right to freedom of expression and freedom of thought / consciousness: beliefs, culture and religion (the right to religion)

Communication with elderly patients in the context of care involves a set of recommendations based on optimizing interactions between specialists and the elderly people:

1. expresses understanding, compassion and patience to help older people cope with the fear and uncertainty of aging and helplessness;
2. questions are asked about living conditions and social contacts, as well as the relationship with close relatives or the couple's relationship;
3. includes elderly patients in conversation even in the presence of relatives / family members and especially life partners;
4. personalize care by seeking information about the beliefs and cultural values of elderly patients related to illness and death;
5. involves the elderly in the process of making decisions related to housing, inheritance, health;
6. the assumptions of old age are avoided when providing information and recommendations on preventive care;
7. patient information is important, but how you convey the information is even more important;
8. a direct, concrete, action-focused language is used;
9. it is checked what the elderly people understood and retained in the conversation.

Vulnerable elderly people are encouraged to participate as much as possible and should be informed about the risks and possible benefits if they are taken decision to live lonely. Social workers are attentive to the principles of privacy, confidentiality and responsible use of information in their professional work, taking into account the age-specific vulnerability, the social aspects specific to the elderly people, they need to communicate more often with the members of their family.

Maria-Mădălina Bodescu stated that for the elderly, it can be stated that the need for communication is vital, its existence, quality and duration of life being threatened by the dissatisfaction of the need for communication, as well as by an inadequate communication. Sooner or later, an elderly person lives the last part of his life, which precedes the end, ending his existence. Communication, at this stage, has particular meanings and is, along with other elements of palliative care, a solution to the quality of life until the last moment.

With the help of communication can determine the type of person, psychological changes caused by aging, their degree of illness, suffering, social and psychological stress, disability. Communication provides valuable data on the needs of one person or another. Also, with the help of communication we can influence even in a therapeutic (psychotherapeutic) sense the person's condition, without taking into account the transmission for appropriation of our messages intended to help him (Bodescu 2007).

Article 6 in the European Charter talking about the right to continuous communication, participation and cultural activity of elderly people when they get old and depend on others on support and care, they continue to have the right to interact with others, and to participate in civic life, teaching self-learning. The elderly has the right to all the support all need to communicate. The elderly has the right to have all communication needs considered and perspectives, no matter how they are expressed (European Charter 2010,4-14). Life has taught us that old age is the price we must pay to attain wisdom, and humiliating the elderly means humiliating our own projection into the future. It is important to learn the art of aging.

Conclusions

Unlike other types of communication interactions, for example, personal or social, communication with older people has its own significant characteristics and attributes. Assigning such features allows you to provide a more specific and complete definition of the concept of “communication with the elderly”. Respect for the ethics of caring for the elderly is being successfully determined today.

Biberi (1970,163). states that by being able to transcend himself, through communication with peers and through social cooperation, man mentally transcends the corner of the world where he appeared The progressive aging of the world's population has major social and economic consequences that will be crucial in the coming decades (CNPV 2013, 18), and communication skills with the elderly are an art that we must all possess.

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